

Dynamical Similarity in Multitasking RNNs: Identifying Shared Motifs Across Task Periods

Rabia Muhammad^{1†}, Seidi Yonamine Yamauti^{1,2†}, Akanksha Gupta^{1,3†}, Moein Khajehnejad^{1,4*}

¹Neuromatch Academy, Neuromatch, Inc., ²Neurology and Neurosciences Department, Federal University of Sao Paulo, Sao Paulo, Brazil, ³Aix-Marseille University, Inserm, Institut de Neurosciences des Systèmes (INS), Marseille, France, ⁴Turner Institute for Brain & Mental Health, Monash Data Future Institute, Monash University.

*e-mail: rbamhd@gmail.com, seidi.yamauti@gmail.com, emailakankshagupta@gmail.com, moein.khajehnejad@monash.edu

†: R.M., S.Y.Y., and A.G. contributed equally.

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Author contributions

R.M., S.Y.Y., and A.G. conceived of the study and developed the analyses. R.M., S.Y.Y., and A.G. analyzed the data. M.K. advised analyses. R.M., S.Y.Y., and A.G. wrote the manuscript, and all authors edited the manuscript.

Keywords

Dynamical Motifs; Dynamic Similarity Analysis; Multi-tasking Recurrent Neural Networks; Dynamic Mode Decomposition

Abstract

Biological networks exhibit remarkable flexibility, enabling efficient multitasking. This study investigates the role of dynamical motifs in facilitating this adaptability within recurrent neural networks (RNNs). Instead of focusing on geometric structures, we employ Dynamic Similarity Analysis (DSA) to reveal underlying dynamic patterns. Applying DSA to the internal states of RNNs across 15 tasks, we identify the delayed response motif as particularly distinct, characterized by unique rotational properties. Our findings highlight DSA's ability to uncover differences overlooked by geometric methods, offering deeper insights into the computational mechanisms underlying both biological and artificial intelligence systems.

Introduction

Biological networks exhibit flexibility, enabling them to adapt and perform efficiently across a wide range of tasks. It has been shown in a multitasking recurrent neural network (RNN) that this flexibility might arise due to sharing and repurposing dynamical motifs such as fixed points and attractors across tasks with similar demands (Driscoll et al., 2024).

Dynamical motifs propose an essential syntax of computation, and can be useful in addressing 'black-box' interpretability problems in AI, as well as allow us to infer how biological networks accomplish flexibility across different tasks. Dynamical motifs are characterized by their spatial structure and position in state space. While the geometries

of the fixed points are shared across different tasks, it's crucial to study the surrounding dynamics.

Most methods used in neuroscience research such as representational similarity analysis (Kriegeskorte et al., 2008), singular vector canonical correlation analysis (Raghu et al., 2017), linear regression and pearson correlation (Schrimpf et al., 2018), centered kernel alignment (Kornblith et al., 2019), and procrustes analysis (Williams et al., 2022) rely solely on the geometric structure of the data to quantify similarity. While these approaches provide valuable insights into representational alignment, they do not capture the underlying dynamical mechanisms governing neural computations. A way to access the underlying dynamics is by using dynamic similarity analysis (DSA) on a multitasking network that repurposes dynamical motifs across tasks (Ostrow et al., 2024).

Dynamic Similarity Analysis (DSA) provides a quantitative measure of the similarity between two dynamical systems by comparing their underlying dynamics. This method capitalizes on the ability of high-dimensional embeddings to represent nonlinear systems within a globally linear framework. Central to this approach are Koopman Modes (Mezić, 2005), which serve as key features enabling this transformation and can be identified using Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) (Brunton et al., 2016; Snyder & Song, 2021). The primary objective of DMD is to construct a finite approximation of the Koopman operator (Ostrow et al., 2024).

Once the systems are mapped into the Koopman Mode space, DSA employs a statistical shape analysis metric to compare their vector fields, effectively quantifying the degree of similarity in their dynamic behavior (Ostrow et al., 2024). By leveraging this approach, DSA provides insights into the fundamental nature of algorithmic substrates and non-spatial features that may not be fully captured by traditional geometric methods.

Methods

Network Structure and Tasks

We utilized vanilla continuous-time recurrent neural networks (RNNs) trained on 15 cognitive tasks, as described by Driscoll et al. (2024) (Figure 1A). These tasks were categorized into five distinct subgroups based on correspondence to similar cognitive experimental tasks (Yang et al., 2019):

- **Decision-Making Tasks (5 tasks):** These tasks consisted of sequential components, including context, stimulus 1, memory 1, stimulus 2, memory 2, and response. The specific tasks were labelled as `delaydm1`, `delaydm2`, `contextdelaydm1`, `contextdelaydm2`, and `multidelaydm`.
- **Delay Match Tasks (4 tasks):** These tasks followed a sequence of context, stimulus 1, memory 1, and either stimulus 2 or response. The tasks were labelled as `dmsgo`, `dmsnogo`, `dmcgo`, and `dmcnogo`.
- **Reaction Time Tasks (2 tasks):** These tasks included fixation, stimulus presentation, and a go/anti-go decision. The tasks were labelled as `reactgo` and `reactanti`.

- **Memory Response Tasks (2 tasks):** These tasks included context, stimulus 1, memory 1, and response. The tasks were labelled as delaygo and delayanti.
- **Delay-Response Tasks (2 tasks):** These tasks followed a sequence of context, stimulus 1, and response. The tasks were labelled as fdgo and fdanti.

Analysis

For our analysis, we applied Dynamic Systems Analysis to the internal states of the trained networks during inference. The DSA algorithm enabled us to assess how network dynamics evolved in response to varying task contexts and inputs across different task periods.

Hyperparameter Optimization

To optimize DSA performance, we performed a grid search over various delay values and ranks, evaluating reconstruction metrics from DMD-decomposed signals, including mean absolute error (MAE), mean absolute scaled error (MASE), mean squared error (MSE), coefficient of determination (R^2), correlation coefficient, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), and logMSE. While higher ranks generally improved reconstruction, increasing the number of delays slightly reduced performance, likely due to interactions between Hankel matrix construction and the delay embedding window size. Based on these findings, we selected the highest-ranked value (5) and an intermediate delay value (5) for the final DSA matrix.

Clustering

We used the Ward minimization algorithm to sort rows and columns of the DSA matrix according to similarity, to ensure consistency with previous work (Driscoll et al., 2024). This was implemented in Python using the function `scipy.cluster.hierarchy.linkage` with Euclidean metric and default threshold. This resulted in a dendrogram representing hierarchical distance of rows and columns in the variance matrix.

For our analysis, we applied DSA to the internal states of the trained networks, for each task period during inference. The DSA algorithm allows us to evaluate how network dynamics evolve in response to varying task contexts and inputs (see Figure 1A)

Results

We performed DSA on the internal states of the RNN during each task period (Figure 1A). This analysis yielded a DSA matrix of all pairwise comparisons between task periods, which were further organized by the task periods of each individual motif. Applying Ward's hierarchical clustering algorithm to this matrix revealed that the DSA for the delayed response motif is more distinguished from all other motifs, with a difference in DSA value of 0.20 (Figure 1B).

The delayed response motif is characterized by a ring of marginally stable fixed points that rotate into output potent space to elicit nonzero values in the output units (Ostrow et al., 2024). This motif often shares the same fixed points as the continuous memory motif but appears separately in the task period DSA matrix due to these points occupying a different subspace. Our results suggest that DSA is capable of

distinguishing the rotational dynamics of this motif during the RNN's internal states during inference.

The other motifs identified in the original study include:

1. Pro stimulus: Results in a response to the initial stimulus, mapping it into the same response orientation.
2. Anti stimulus: Results in a response to the initial stimulus, mapping it into the opposite response orientation.
3. Stimulus categorization: Divides the initial continuous stimulus into categories based on the experimenter-chosen category boundary.
4. Stimulus integration: Integration of contextual information from different modalities.
5. Continuous memory: A ring of marginally stable fixed points holds the neural state in place following a stimulus period.
6. Category memory: Two-point attractors hold the neural state in place following a stimulus period.
7. Reaction-timed response: Stable fixed points in output potent space elicit nonzero values in the output units.

The key distinction between the delayed response motif and the other motifs lies in its unique rotational dynamics and the transition of fixed points from one subspace to another. While other motifs may involve stable fixed points (e.g., continuous memory, category memory) or direct mappings of stimuli to responses (e.g., pro stimulus, anti

stimulus), the delayed response motif specifically involves a rotation of fixed points into the output potent space, which may account for its distinguishability in the DSA results.

It is important to note that we applied DSA to internal states rather than the principal component space used to characterize motifs in the original study. This methodological difference may affect the interpretation of our results. Future work is required to explore applying DSA within the principal component space, which could offer further insights into the algorithm's ability to capture information about motifs.

Discussion

This study aims to enhance our understanding of dynamical motifs in multitasking recurrent networks by analyzing their dynamics across different cognitive tasks. Building on previous literature, it employs Dynamic Similarity Analysis to identify differences that may not be readily captured by interpolation analysis, thereby revealing key dynamical motifs. For future work, we would like to compare the results obtained by Dynamic Similarity Analysis with other available methods. By focusing on the underlying dynamics, this research seeks to provide insights into the mechanisms enabling multitasking in the brain, with potential implications for both neuroscience and AI.

References

- Brunton, S. L., Brunton, B. W., Proctor, J. L., & Kutz, J. N. (2016). Koopman invariant subspaces and finite linear representations of nonlinear dynamical systems for control. *PLOS ONE*, *11*(2), e0150171. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0150171>
- Driscoll, L. N., Shenoy, K., & Sussillo, D. (2024). Flexible multitask computation in recurrent networks utilizes shared dynamical motifs. *Nature Neuroscience*, *27*(7), 1349–1363. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-024-01668-6>
- Kornblith, S., Norouzi, M., Lee, H., & Hinton, G. (2019). *Similarity of Neural Network Representations Revisited* (arXiv:1905.00414). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1905.00414>
- Kriegeskorte, N., Mur, M., & Bandettini, P. A. (2008). Representational similarity analysis—Connecting the branches of systems neuroscience. *Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience*, *2*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/neuro.06.004.2008>
- Mezić, I. (2005). Spectral Properties of Dynamical Systems, Model Reduction and Decompositions. *Nonlinear Dynamics*, *41*(1), 309–325. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11071-005-2824-x>
- Ostrow, M., Eisen, A., Kozachkov, L., & Fiete, I. (2024). Beyond geometry: Comparing the temporal structure of computation in neural circuits with dynamical similarity analysis. *Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*, 33824–33837.
- Raghu, M., Gilmer, J., Yosinski, J., & Sohl-Dickstein, J. (2017). *SVCCA: Singular Vector Canonical Correlation Analysis for Deep Learning Dynamics and Interpretability* (arXiv:1706.05806). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1706.05806>
- Schrimpf, M., Kumbhani, J., Hong, H., Majaj, N. J., Rajalingham, R., Issa, E. B., Kar, K., Bashivan,

P., Prescott-Roy, J., Geiger, F., Schmidt, K., Yamins, D. L. K., & DiCarlo, J. J. (2018). *Brain-Score: Which Artificial Neural Network for Object Recognition is most Brain-Like?* <https://doi.org/10.1101/407007>

Snyder, G., & Song, Z. (2021). *Koopman Operator Theory for Nonlinear Dynamic Modeling using Dynamic Mode Decomposition* (arXiv:2110.08442). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2110.08442>

Williams, A. H., Kunz, E., Kornblith, S., & Linderman, S. W. (2022). *Generalized Shape Metrics on Neural Representations* (arXiv:2110.14739). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2110.14739>

Yang, G. R., Joglekar, M. R., Song, H. F., Newsome, W. T., & Wang, X.-J. (2019). Task representations in neural networks trained to perform many cognitive tasks. *Nature Neuroscience*, 22(2), 297–306. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-018-0310-2>